

EXPLORING NURSES' EXPERIENCES OF RECOMMENDED PATIENT (VIP)CARE: A DESCRIPTIVE PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY

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Abstract

This qualitative descriptive phenomenology study investigated the lived experiences of nurses caring for recommended (VIP) patients at Tertiary care hospital in Karachi. Caring for VIP patients presents ethical, emotional, and practical issues that frequently contradict the fundamental nursing values of justice, equity, and patient-centered care. Using purposive sampling, twelve registered nurses with at least three years of clinical experience and past involvement in VIP patient care were selected. Data were gathered through semi-structured, in-depth interviews held between October 2025 and March 2026. The interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, and managed using MAXQDA 2020 software. Data were analyzed using thematic analysis guided by Colaizzi's seven-step phenomenological method, while Lincoln and Guba's criteria were used to guarantee reliability. Four main issues emerged from the analysis: excessive workload and logistical stress; emotional and psychological strain; compromised care and ethical conflict; and the need for institutional assistance and structural reform. Significant stress and emotional tiredness from greater scrutiny and contempt, moral discomfort from justice violations and disturbed clinical triage, and increased effort from strict VIP protocols and staffing imbalances were all mentioned by nurses. Clear standard operating procedures, administrative support, patient and attendant education, and specialized VIP personnel were all highly stressed by the participants. The results show that existing VIP care practices jeopardize nurse well-being and equitable healthcare delivery, underscoring the critical need for institutional and policy-level changes to support moral, sustainable, and equitable nursing care for all patients.

INTRODUCTION

In nursing profession, providing care for recommended (VIP) patients presents both professional and emotional problems. It is the duty of nurses to care for patients regardless of their status and position. Therefore, the foundation for improving patient satisfaction may be understanding nurses' experiences managing suggested patients in order to deliver high-quality and efficient treatment. The goal of the current study was to clarify nurses' experiences providing care for patients who were suggested to them. The term "VIP syndrome" refers to the medical, administrative, and organizational difficulties that come with caring for very important people (VIPs), such as celebrities and royalty. A situation that frequently compels the medical staff to alter the guidelines by which they typically deliver treatment (1). The VIP syndrome refers to a pattern of patient demands that result in poor clinical judgment in an effort to satisfy irrational expectations, which can have negative consequences. Expecting particular treatment and placing a greater emphasis on tests and interventions can have negative effects, and this risky cycle is continued by the need for further, frequently needless medical procedures (2). A recommended patient is a unique individual who is suggested to the medical team for more in-depth care due to their reputation, social standing, and family ties (3). Nurses are the largest group of employees providing health services (4). and the main foundation of the process of improving the quality-of-care services. Accordingly, their performance plays a decisive role in the progress of the organization's goal (5). Since patients have the most contact with nurses, some experts attribute the acceptability of health services exclusively to nurses, and the prominent role of other treatment groups is often ignored (6). All patients are important, equal and valued in nursing care. However, VIP patients benefit from greater access to health resources, special attention from staff and luxury amenities. Despite these benefits, caring for VIP patients can also have negative impacts. Caring for VIP patients promotes inequalities and injustices in

healthcare and can create ethical dilemmas for healthcare professionals. Nurses are the healthcare professionals most affected by the demands of VIP patients, their families and administrators to provide specialized care and attention. The nursing care of VIP patients can become overwhelming, challenging, stressful and confusing, causing moral distress in nurses (7). It is the duty of all nurses to facilitate the right of all patients to obtain high-quality care (8). Additionally, nurses need to be held ethically and legally responsible. for the caliber of treatment given (9). A nurse's ability to meet a patient's physical, psychological, emotional, social, and spiritual requirements so they can return to their normal, healthy lives is a measure of the quality of nursing care (10). In the context of the healthcare system, social justice is the provision of equal medical care to all individuals, irrespective of their individual qualities (11). Prior research in this area has demonstrated that VIP patient care is difficult and stressful, and that receiving more attention and having easier access to resources these patients, and unfavorable outcomes such patient injury, care disruption, and heightened workload come after nurses (11). Nevertheless, no research was discovered in this area based on the methodology of this investigation with regard to recommended patients (not VIP). The American Association of Critical Care Nurses (AACN) defines social justice as treating people fairly regardless of their financial situation, race, ethnicity, age, citizenship, sexual orientation, or disability (12). Studies assessing the moral behavior of other medical professionals, particularly doctors, toward VIP patients are widely available, but there aren't many that examine nurses' treatment of VIP patients from an ethical standpoint (13). Analyzing the ethical issues that emerge from the treatment that nurses give VIP patients is therefore vital. The purpose of this review is to help nurses effectively manage ethical issues that come up when providing nursing care for VIP patients by critically analyzing these issues in light of the ethical principles of beneficence,

nonmaleficence, justice, autonomy, and privacy. Regardless of their financial situation, race, ethnicity, age, citizenship, disability, sexual orientation, or personality traits, nurses are required to care for their patients. Occasionally, nurses must care for patients who have been suggested to them. In these situations, the kind and timing of care and the need for additional care is decided by the patients themselves and tailored to their individual goals. The suggested patient treatment typically results in a deviation from standard care practices, which eventually makes the care team fearful. Prior research has demonstrated the application of phenomenology to investigate experiences pertaining to particular instances, including end-of-life care, critical patient care, and caring with COVID-19 patients (7, 14-18). The focus of phenomenology is on individuals' perceptions or interpretations of living experiences. Furthermore, investigating other people's experiences can yield previously undiscovered insights, making it a valuable approach for this research. This approach offers a thorough comprehension of how nurses tend to patients who are advised. The searches turned up no qualitative studies about nurses' experiences caring for patients who were advised. The current study was carried out with the intention of examining the significance and character of nurses' experiences of suggested patient care since their knowledge and insight on the experience of caring for these patients can aid in planning for similar patients. This study describes the difficulties nurses face when caring for patients who have been recommended (VIP), including job overload, discrimination, poor prognosis, and emotional strain. These results highlight the necessity of moving the emphasis from patient labeling to universal, egalitarian, and legally-based care. Enhancing the work environment, encouraging cultural change, and putting in place focused training programs that empower nurses and encourage efficient, compassionate care are all crucial for raising nurse satisfaction and care quality (18).

Literature review

The topic of caring for recommended or very important person (VIP) patients has received a lot of attention in the healthcare literature because of the ethical, clinical, and organizational problems it offers. The term VIP syndrome was coined to characterize instances in which healthcare workers deviate from normal clinical practices in reaction to patients' social position, power, or influence, frequently compromising clinical judgment and patient safety (19). VIP patients frequently have preferential access to resources, more attention, and deviations from usual protocols, which can disrupt equitable care delivery and present ethical quandaries for healthcare workers (20).

According to Beauchamp & Childress (2019) and the International Council of Nurses [ICN], 2021, nursing ethics place a strong emphasis on fairness, equality, and patient-centered care, requiring nurses to give all patients impartial, superior care regardless of their social or economic background (21). However, research shows that by putting non-clinical considerations ahead of patient needs, VIP care frequently transgresses these ethical standards (22). When institutional expectations collide with professional beliefs, nurses are especially susceptible to ethical conflict because they are the frontline caregivers who interact with patients the most (23).

One well-researched effect of these ethical dilemmas in nursing practice is moral anguish. According to (24), moral anguish is the psychological discomfort that arises when medical professionals are aware of the morally right course of action but are unable to take it because of organizational limitations. Further research has connected moral distress to burnout, emotional tiredness, a decline in job satisfaction, and a desire to quit one's career (25). According to research, providing care for VIP patients increases moral anguish because nurses are under pressure to meet demands for preferential treatment that go against their moral convictions. The literature has also emphasized the emotional and psychological stress experienced by nurses who provide care for VIP patients. According to

(26) nurses often report increased stress as a result of ongoing surveillance, anxiety of making mistakes, and hostile or disrespectful conduct from patients' family and attendants. These encounters damage nurses' sense of self and dignity as professionals, which leads to emotional exhaustion and lower treatment quality. These pressures are made worse by workplace rudeness and a lack of managerial support, especially in hierarchical healthcare environments (27).

VIP care is linked to higher burden and ineffective resource allocation from an operational standpoint. According to studies, allocating several nurses to a single stable VIP patient results in staffing imbalances, adds to the workload of existing staff, and has a detrimental impact on patient outcomes (28). In VIP care settings, excessive protocol requirements and administrative monitoring further interfere with regular nursing tasks and lower overall productivity (29). These difficulties jeopardize patient safety, care continuity, and nurse well-being.

Despite increased awareness of these problems, the majority of current research concentrates on doctors' experiences with VIP patients, paying little attention to nurses' viewpoints, especially in low- and middle-income nations (30). Additionally, there aren't many qualitative phenomenology research that examine nurses' actual experiences providing care for patients who are recommended rather than officially declared VIPs. It is crucial to comprehend these experiences in order to create care models that are moral, just, and long-lasting. By examining nurses' actual experiences of caring for recommended (VIP) patients, this study aims to close this gap and offer insights that will guide institutional reform, policy formulation, and ethical nursing practice.

2. Methodology

This study will adopt a qualitative research design using a descriptive phenomenological approach to explore the lived experiences of nurses caring for recommended (VIP) patients in 2025. A phenomenological design is appropriate as it allows for an in-depth understanding of

participants' subjective experiences and perceptions within their real clinical context. The study will be conducted at Tertiary care Hospital, Karachi, and the study participants will comprise 12 registered nurses working in different hospital settings within the institution. Participants will be selected based on predefined inclusion criteria: having a minimum of three years of clinical experience, prior experience in providing care to recommended (VIP) patients, current clinical practice or practice within the last 12 months, and willingness to participate with informed consent. Nurses without direct patient care experience, those working exclusively in administrative, academic, or research roles, and nurses with no experience in caring for recommended patients will be excluded from the study.

A non-probability purposive sampling technique will be employed to recruit participants who can provide rich and relevant data aligned with the study objectives. Data collection will be carried out through semi-structured, in-depth, face-to-face interviews, which will be audio-recorded with participants' consent. Interviews will be conducted at a mutually agreed-upon location to ensure privacy and comfort, and a supportive environment will be established by initiating informal conversation prior to the interview. An interview guide developed specifically for this study will be used to ensure consistency while allowing flexibility for participants to freely express their experiences. Each interview will begin with the open-ended question, "Can you tell me about your experience of caring for recommended patients?" Probing questions such as "why," "how," and "please explain further" will be used to gain deeper insights and clarify emerging concepts. Interviews are expected to last between 30 and 60 minutes, depending on participants' responses and engagement.

3. Data analysis and result

Data management will be facilitated using MAXQDA 2020 software. Data analysis will follow Colaizzi's seven-step phenomenological method to systematically identify significant statements, formulate meanings, and develop

themes that reflect the essence of participants' experiences. To ensure rigor and trustworthiness, the study will adhere to Lincoln and Guba's criteria, including credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability. The data collection and sampling process is anticipated to take approximately six months, from October 2025 to March 2026. This methodological approach is expected to generate comprehensive and meaningful insights into nurses' experiences of caring for recommended patients within a hospital setting.

Consolidated Thematic Analysis of Nurses' Lived Experience with VIP Patient Care.

A thematic analysis of 12 semi-structured interviews with nurses from Tertiary care Hospital revealed four overarching themes that describe the ethical tensions, emotional burden, logistical challenges, and systemic reforms needed when caring for VIP patients under institutional protocol. These themes reflect the complex intersection between clinical care, hierarchical expectations, and workplace culture within the hospital environment.

Table 1. General Characteristics of Participants (N= 12)

Participant	Gender	Marital Status	Age (Years)	Workplace Ward	Educational Level	Work Experience (Years)
P1	Female	Un married	27 Y	VIP/Officers' Ward	BSN	04 YEARS
P2	Female	Un married	28 Y	VIP/Officers' Ward	BSN	4.5 YEAR
P3	Female	Un married	29 Y	VIP/Officers' Ward	BSN	05 YEARS
P4	Male	Un married	25 Y	VIP/Officers' Ward	BSN	03 YEARS
P5	Female	Un married	26 Y	VIP/Officers' Ward	BSN	04 YEARS
P6	Female	Un married	28 Y	VIP/Officers' Ward	BSN	06 YEARS
P7	Female	Married	30 Y	Officers' Ward 5	BSN	08 YEARS
P8	Male	Un married	27 Y	VIP/Officers' Ward	BSN	05 YEARS
P9	Female	Un married	27 Y	VIP/Officers' Ward	BSN	05 YEARS
P10	Female	Un married	28 Y	VIP/Officers' Ward	BSN	06 YEARS
P11	Female	Un married	25 Y	VIP/Officers' Ward	BSN	04 YEARS
P12	Female	Un married	27 Y	VIP/Officers' Ward	BSN	05 YEARS

Table 2. Theme and Sub Themes.

Theme	Subtheme	Supporting/Evidence (Codes/Synthesized Findings)
Theme 1: Compromised Care and Ethical Conflict	1.1 Neglect of General Patients	Attention to VIP patients inevitably slows down care for the rest of the ward
		Routine care for general patients is frequently delayed or disrupted when VIP-related requests escalate or when attendants create “a lot of fuss
		At times, a whole ward’s workflow becomes centered around a single VIP patient, resulting in compromised patient safety and delayed interventions.
	1.2 Violation of Justice and Equality	Nurses articulated a strong belief that all patients are equal according to nursing ethics.
		The requirement to prioritize a stable VIP patient over a critically ill non-VIP patient contradicts their professional values and creates emotional conflict
		The practice was described as “wrong” and fundamentally incompatible with the principle of justice
	1.3 Protocol-Based Triage	The VIP culture influences clinical triage, even in emergency settings.
		Nurses described instances where a more senior or high-status VIP patient is attended to first, while a critically ill patient is left waiting—representing a structural distortion of clinical priorities
Theme 2: Emotional and Psychological Strain	2.1 Stress, Anxiety, and Constant Pressure	The environment around VIP care is described as highly stressful.
		Pressure comes from multiple sources: administration, nursing in-charges, senior staff, patients, and attendants.

		The fear of mistakes (“no room for error”), constant scrutiny, and continuous demands contribute to anxiety and exhaustion
	2.2 Disrespect, Aggression, and Undermined Professionalism	Nurses frequently experience rude, aggressive, or demeaning behavior from VIP attendants
		Attendants question every intervention, demand detailed explanations, dismiss the nurse’s competence, and insist a doctor perform simple task
		Some participants described being treated like “servants” or “slaves,” which erodes professional dignity and demotivates nurses
	2.3 VIP Superiority and Behavioral Challenges	VIP patients and their families are often perceived as “attention seekers” who “throw tantrums” and expect immediate fulfillment of all demands
		They compare the hospital to a “restaurant”
		Nurses noted that patients start considering themselves “superior” once the VIP protocol begins.
Theme 3: Unmanageable Workload and Logistical Burden	3.1 Disruption of Routine and Time Consumption	Caring for a VIP patient can consume half or more of an 8-hour shift, even when the patient is stable
		This time consumption is primarily due to protocol requirements rather than clinical need
		Routine nursing activities for the rest of the ward are often delayed or abandoned.
	3.2 Staffing Shortages and Increased Personnel Demand	The requirement to allocate two to three nurses for a single VIP patient creates a significant imbalance in manpower distribution

		The rest of the ward is left understaffed, intensifying strain on remaining nurses
	3.3 Heavy Protocol Compliance and Administrative Monitoring	VIP care requires extensive planning and “homework”
		Nurses must perform tasks more cautiously (“IV in one prick”) and follow strict etiquette (e.g., knocking before entering)
		Staff are constantly responding to minor requests (remote control, AC adjustments, immediate lab follow-ups), which makes routine care more complicated and time-intensive
Theme 4: Demand for Institutional Support and Systemic Reform	4.1 Dedicated VIP Staffing	The most consistent recommendation is that VIP patients should have separate designated staff
		Nurses emphasized that it is impossible to care for both the VIP patient and the rest of the ward simultaneously without compromising care.
	4.2 Management Support, SOPs, and Accountability	nurses strongly desire Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for VIP care
		They need guidelines that protect nurses’ dignity, fair investigation of complaints (not one-sided), and administrative backing against rude attendants
		They expressed that management often blames the nurse first instead of understanding the full situation
	4.3 Patient and Attendant Education	Many issues could be reduced if VIP patients and families were patient and cooperative.
		They should understand that a hospital is not a hotel or restaurant and avoid unnecessary demands.
		Nurses suggested awareness sessions or communication guidelines for attendants.

Table 3: Thematic Analysis of Nurses’ Lived Experience of VIP Patient Care

Theme No.	Main Theme	Subthemes / Key Issues Identified
Theme 1	Compromised Care & Ethical Conflict	Neglect of general patients, Violation of justice, Distorted triage decisions
Theme 2	Emotional & Psychological Strain	Stress and pressure, Disrespect and aggression from attendants, Perceived VIP superiority
Theme 3	Workload & Logistical Burden	Disrupted routine nursing care, Staffing shortages, Heavy protocol and documentation demands
Theme 4	Demand for Institutional Support & Systemic Reform	Dedicated staff for VIP patients, Clear SOPs and administrative backing, Education of patients and attendants, Need for ethical, sustainable, and equitable care systems

The thematic map can be seen in figure 1.

Figure 1: The thematic map of nurses lived experience of VIP patient care

4. Findings and Discussion

The results of this descriptive phenomenological study highlight important ethical, emotional, and organizational obstacles and offer a comprehensive knowledge of nurses lived experiences in caring for recommended (VIP) patients. Because recommended patients frequently received preferential treatment, nurses frequently claimed that VIP care practices harmed equitable patient care by delaying or disrupting care for regular patients. The

fundamental tenets of nursing ethics—justice and equality—were clearly at odds with this practice (Beauchamp & Childress, 2019; International Council of Nurses [ICN], 2021). Similar results by (31), describing how VIP syndrome might skew clinical judgment and result in departures from normal care practices, possibly jeopardizing patient safety.

The moral pain nurses felt when forced to give stable VIP patients priority over clinically critical non-VIP patients was one of the study's most

notable findings. When nurses understand what is morally right to do but are prevented from doing so by institutional rules or pressure from higher-ups, moral discomfort results (32). The participants' reports of emotional conflict, guilt, and ethical discomfort are consistent with earlier research showing that sustained moral distress increases nurses' intentions to leave their jobs, burnout, and job satisfaction (33).

Another important issue was emotional and psychological strain, with nurses reporting ongoing stress, anxiety, and emotional tiredness as a result of increased scrutiny, a fear of making mistakes, and rude behavior from VIP patients and their attendants. These results are in line with studies showing that verbal abuse, workplace rudeness, and a lack of professional respect have a detrimental impact on nurses' performance and mental health (34). A power disparity that compromises professional identity and adds to emotional exhaustion is reflected in participants' experiences of being treated more like "servants" than as healthcare professionals.

The excessive strain and logistical stress related to VIP care were also addressed in the study. Staffing mismatches, an increase in effort for the remaining personnel, and disruptions to routine care activities resulted from assigning many nurses to a single stable VIP patient. They (28) have found similar problems, emphasizing that patient outcomes and nurse well-being are negatively impacted by limited staffing and unbalanced workload distribution. Nurses' workload was further increased by ongoing administrative oversight and excessive protocol requirements, which decreased productivity and raised stress levels.

Crucially, nurses were ardent supporters of systemic change and institutional support. The necessity of specialized VIP staffing, unambiguous standard operating procedures, managerial responsibility, and patient and attendant education was underlined by the participants. The literature that is currently available supports these suggestions, indicating that moral leadership, supportive management, and established guidelines are critical for lowering moral distress and fostering equitable

care environments (35). It has also been demonstrated that educating patients and their families about hospital procedures and polite communication enhances nurse-patient relationships and lessens conflict (36).

Overall, the results of this study show that VIP care as it is now provided leads to operational inefficiencies, emotional strain, and ethical dilemmas that jeopardize nurses' professional integrity and patient equality. To address these issues and guarantee long-term, patient-centered, and justice-based nursing care, organizations must be committed to ethical practice, equitable resource distribution, and supportive governance.

5. Conclusion

This descriptive phenomenological study comes to the conclusion that providing care for recommended (VIP) patients puts nurses in emotionally taxing, operationally difficult, and ethically complex situations that have a substantial impact on the standard of care as well as the nurses' professional well-being. The results show that by putting social status ahead of clinical necessity, VIP care practices frequently violate the ideals of justice and equity, resulting in moral suffering, emotional tiredness, and disturbed nursing workflows. Due to high demands, staffing imbalances, and insufficient managerial support, nurses face increasing pressure, a heavier workload, and a lost sense of professional dignity. Crucially, the report emphasizes that systemic and organizational structures that control VIP care are the source of these difficulties rather than individual nursing behavior. The necessity of institutional improvements, such as specialized VIP personnel, standard operating procedures, administrative accountability, and patient and attendant education, was succinctly expressed by the participants. In order to protect nurses' professional integrity, ensure high-quality care for all patients, regardless of social class, and advance ethical, egalitarian, and sustainable nursing care, it is imperative that these policies be put into practice.

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